

Study notes on dynamic systems

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This document is a collection of my study notes on Dr. Luenberger's book: Dynamics Systems. I write this document for myself and others who are interested in using quantitative tools to study dynamic and multi-variable natural phenomena. Dr. Luenberger has a background in electrical engineering. However, throughout his book numerous example problems are drawn from such diverse academic fields, including biology and ecology, that I am sure that this book has a broad impact in science.

1 Some important formulas

The central focus of Dr. Luenberger's book is applied differential/difference equations and linear algebra for formulating, solving and analyzing equations describing the dynamics of multi-variable natural phenomena. It assumes a familiarity of calculus. The following are frequently used formulas in many instances:

1. General Maclaurin expansion of functions. Given $f(x)$, we have

$$M(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{[f(x)]^j}{j!}. \quad (1)$$

For exponential function e^x , the expansion is

$$e^x = 1 + x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots \quad (2)$$

Here are the expansions for $\sin \theta$ and $\cos \theta$:

$$\sin \theta = \theta - \frac{\theta^3}{3!} + \frac{\theta^5}{5!} - \dots, \cos \theta = 1 - \frac{\theta^2}{2!} + \frac{\theta^4}{4!} - \dots \quad (3)$$

2. A useful trigonometrical relationship:

$$\sin \alpha \pm \sin \beta = 2 \sin \frac{1}{2}(\alpha \pm \beta) \cos \frac{1}{2}(\alpha \mp \beta) \quad (4)$$

3. Hyperbolic sin and cos functions are related to the exponential function by

$$\sinh x = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{2}, \cosh x = \frac{e^x + e^{-x}}{2}. \quad (5)$$

4. The sin and cos functions are related to the complex exponential function by

$$\sin x = \frac{e^{ix} - e^{-ix}}{2i}, \cos x = \frac{e^{ix} + e^{-ix}}{2}, \quad (6)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

5. Two matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are *similar* if $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{P}^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}$, where \mathbf{P} is called similarity transformation. Similar matrices share many important properties:

- (a) Rank (maximum number of linear independent columns);
- (b) Trace (sum of diagonal elements of square matrices);
- (c) Determinant (the matrix analog of the absolute value);
- (d) Eigenvalues¹ (but generally not eigenvectors); and
- (e) Characteristic polynomials.

6. Properties about traces of square matrices:

$$\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{A}^T), \text{tr}(\mathbf{AB}) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{B})\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}) \quad (7)$$

7. Remember the following useful properties about matrix transpose and inverse:

$$(\mathbf{AB})^T = \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{A}^T, (\mathbf{AB})^{-1} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

8. If $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ are eigenvalues of an $n \times n$ square matrix with real or complex entries, then

$$\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}) = \sum_i \lambda_i, \text{tr}(\mathbf{A}^k) = \sum_i \lambda_i^k, \det(\mathbf{A}) = \prod \lambda_i. \quad (9)$$

¹“Eigen” in German means “self”. Every vector is an eigenvector of identity matrix \mathbf{I} , with corresponding eigenvalue of unity.

9. For symmetric matrix \mathbf{R} , $[\mathbf{R}^{-1}]^T = \mathbf{R}^{-1}$. This is because $\mathbf{R}\mathbf{R}^{-1} = \mathbf{I}$, but $[\mathbf{R}\mathbf{R}^{-1}]^T = [\mathbf{R}^{-1}]^T\mathbf{R}^T = [\mathbf{R}^{-1}]^T\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{I}$.
10. Inverse of a diagonal matrix is the matrix with individual diagonal elements of the original matrix being inverted. If

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix}, \text{ then}$$

$$\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/a_{11} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 1/a_{22} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1/a_{nn} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

11. Euler's definition of $e^{i\theta}$ (under polar coordinate):

$$e^{i\theta} = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta \Rightarrow e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0 \quad (11)$$

The last equation (above) includes five most important numbers in mathematics (e , π , i , 1 and 0) in one equation.

12. The magnitude of a complex exponential is its real part. This is because

$$\begin{aligned} |e^z| &= |e^{a+ib}| \\ &= |e^a| \cdot |\cos b + i \sin b| \\ &= |e^a| \sqrt{\cos^2 b + \sin^2 b} \\ &= e^a \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

13. Formula of integration by parts:

$$\int u dv = uv - \int v du \quad (13)$$

2 Important facts about symmetric matrix and diagonal matrix

1. ² If a square matrix \mathbf{A} equals to its transpose ($\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^T$, and for every entry of \mathbf{A} , $a_{ij} = a_{ji}$), it is called a symmetric matrix.

²The material of section is due to http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Symmetric_matrix, and pages 81-82 and 351-352 of the Luenberger book.

2. Every diagonal matrix is symmetric, because all off-diagonal entries are zero's. Similarly, each diagonal entry of a *skew-symmetric matrix* (one in which $a_{ij} = -a_{ji}$), since each is its own negative.
3. An orthogonal matrix is a square matrix in which the columns and rows are orthogonal unit vectors. Equivalently, a matrix \mathbf{Q} is orthogonal if its transpose equals to its inverse ($\mathbf{Q}^T = \mathbf{Q}^{-1}$, which entails that $\mathbf{Q}^T\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{Q}^T = \mathbf{I}$, \mathbf{I} being the identity matrix).
4. For every symmetric matrix \mathbf{A} there exists a real orthogonal matrix \mathbf{Q} such that $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{Q}^T\mathbf{A}\mathbf{Q}$ is a diagonal matrix. Symmetric matrix is thus, up to the choice of an orthogonal basis, a diagonal matrix.
5. Further, as shown in pages 81-82 of the Luenberger book, any square matrix \mathbf{A} with distinct eigenvectors can be put in diagonal form by a change of basis: i.e., $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{M}$, where $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is a diagonal matrix with its main diagonal occupied by the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} :

$$\mathbf{\Lambda} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \lambda_n \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

In the above, \mathbf{M} is called the modal matrix, having \mathbf{A} 's eigenvectors as its n columns:

$$\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{e}_1 \ \mathbf{e}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{e}_n]. \quad (15)$$

Alternatively, any square matrix with distinct eigenvectors can be expressed in terms of its eigenvalues and eigenvectors:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{M}^{-1}. \quad (16)$$

6. The sum and difference of two symmetric matrices is again symmetric, but this is not always the case for the product: given symmetric matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{AB} is symmetric if and only if \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} commute, i.e., if $\mathbf{AB} = \mathbf{BA}$. As a result, for integer n , \mathbf{A}^n is symmetric if \mathbf{A} is symmetric.
7. If \mathbf{A}^{-1} exists, it is symmetric if \mathbf{A} is symmetric.
8. An $n \times n$ symmetric matrix \mathbf{A} is determined by $n(n+1)/2$ scalars (the number of entries on and above the main diagonal). This is because there are n entries on the main diagonal and $(n^2 - n)/2$ entries located

above the main diagonal. So, the total number of entries located on and above the main diagonal is thus $n + (n^2 - n)/2 = n(n + 1)/2$. A symmetric matrix can be expressed as $\mathbf{X} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{X}^T)$.

9. Similarly, a skew-symmetric matrix is determined by $n(n - 1)/2$ scalars (the number of entries above the main diagonal). It can be expressed as $\mathbf{X} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}^T)$.
10. Every quadratic form \mathbf{q} on \mathbf{R}^n can be uniquely written in the form $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}$, in where \mathbf{A} is $n \times n$ symmetric matrix. As \mathbf{A} can be put in diagonal form through changing basis, one can say that,

$$\mathbf{q}(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i x_i^2. \quad (17)$$

11. For symmetric matrix $\mathbf{P}(t)$, the partial derivative of the quadratic form $\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P}(t) \mathbf{x}$ with respect to vector \mathbf{x} is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{x}} [\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P}(t) \mathbf{x}] = 2\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P}(t). \quad (18)$$

12. A symmetric matrix \mathbf{P} is positive semidefinite if and only if all its eigenvalues are nonnegative. It is positive definite if and only if the eigenvalues are strictly positive. Alternatively, \mathbf{P} is positive semidefinite if the associated quadratic form $\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x}$ is positive semidefinite (i.e., $\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x} \geq 0$). It is positive definite if $\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x} > 0$ (see pages 350-352).
13. The distributive rule can be applied to two or more quadratic forms involving symmetric matrices $\mathbf{P}(t)$, $\mathbf{Q}(t)$, ..., etc. (see Eq. (11.75) on page 425 of the Luenberger book).

$$\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P}(t) \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{Q}(t) \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}^T (\mathbf{P}(t) + \mathbf{Q}(t)) \mathbf{x}. \quad (19)$$

3 Laplace transform and z-transform

The Laplace transform and z-transform relate functions in *time domain* to the ones in *frequency domain* in continuous and discrete times, respectively. They are useful in solving some differential and difference equations, because in some instances the functional relationship in frequency domain can be

Table 1: Selected Laplace transform pairs for general function $f(x)$ (Source: S. Boyd, www.stanford.edu/~boyd/ee102/laplace-table.pdf).

Original function: $f(x)$	Laplace transform: $F(s)$
$f + g$	$F + G$
αf	αF
$\frac{df}{dt}$	$sF(s) - f(0)$
$\frac{d^k f}{dt^k}$	$s^k F(s) - s^{k-1} f(0) - s^{k-2} \frac{df}{dt}(0) - \dots - \frac{d^{k-1} f}{dt^{k-1}}(0)$
$g(t) = \int_0^t f(\tau) d\tau$	$G(s) = \frac{F(s)}{s}$
$f(\alpha t), \alpha > 0$	$\frac{1}{\alpha} F(s/\alpha)$
$e^{at} f(t)$	$F(s - a)$
$t f(t)$	$-\frac{dF}{ds}$
$t^k f(t)$	$(-1)^k \frac{d^k F(s)}{ds^k}$
$\frac{f(t)}{t}$	$\int_0^\infty F(s) ds$

Table 2: Some useful Laplace transform pairs useful for solving some forms of ordinary differential equations (Source: S. Boyd, www.stanford.edu/~boyd/ee102/laplace-table.pdf).

Original function: $f(x)$	Laplace transform: $F(s)$
1	$\frac{1}{s}$
t	$\frac{1}{s^2}$
t^n	$\frac{n!}{s^{n+1}}$
$\frac{t^k}{k!}, k \geq 0$	$\frac{1}{s^{k+1}}$
e^{at}	$\frac{1}{s-a}$
e^{-t}	$\frac{1}{(s+1)^2}$
$\cos \omega t$	$\frac{s}{s^2+\omega^2}$
$\sin \omega t$	$\frac{\omega}{s^2+\omega^2}$
$e^{-at} \cos \omega t$	$\frac{s+a}{(s+a)^2+\omega^2}$
$e^{-at} \sin \omega t$	$\frac{\omega}{(s+a)^2+\omega^2}$

simpler than those under the usual time domain. For example, through Laplace transform, the functions involving differentials/integrals, or those involving multiplications between sin/cos and exponential functions, can be converted into functions containing simpler forms.

Given a function $f(x)$, the Laplace transform is defined as

$$F(s) = \int_0^{\infty} f(t) e^{-st} dt, \quad (20)$$

where x and t are continuous.

Given a function $y(k)$ defined on integer series $k = 1, 2, \dots$, a z-transform is defined as

$$Y(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{y(k)}{z^k} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} y(k) z^{-k}. \quad (21)$$

Table 1 and Table 2 list some important and useful examples of the two types of the transforms. One more entry to be added to Table 1 is the Laplace transform for a delayed function:

$$g(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq t < T \\ f(t - T) & t \geq T \end{cases} \quad T \geq 0, \quad G(s) = e^{-sT} F(s). \quad (22)$$

In Table 2 one entry about e^{-t} is based on problem 10(b) of page 311 of the Luenberger book.

The following are important z-transform pairs useful for solving some difference equations (source: Table 8-1 on page 261 of the Luenberger book):

Unit impulse	$f(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & k = 0 \\ 0 & k \geq 1 \end{cases}$	$F(z) = 1$
Unit step	$f(k) = 1$	$F(z) = \frac{z}{z - 1}$
Unit ramp	$f(k) = k$	$F(z) = \frac{z}{(z - 1)^2}$
Geometric series	$f(k) = a^k$	$F(z) = \frac{z}{z - a}$
Geometric ramp	$f(k) = ka^{k-1}$	$F(z) = \frac{z}{(z - a)^2}$

$$\text{Delayed geometric series} \quad f(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & k = 0 \\ a^{k-1} & k > 0 \end{cases} \quad F(z) = \frac{1}{z-a}$$

$$\text{Delayed geometric ramp} \quad f(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & k = 0 \\ (k-1)a^{k-2} & k > 0 \end{cases} \quad F(z) = \frac{1}{(z-a)^2}$$

4 Inverse Laplace and z-transforms

In using Laplace or z-transform to solve differential or difference equations, inverse transform is needed in order to transform back to the original functions (in time domain). The technique of partial fraction expansion is very useful. The general rule is illustrated in the following example. For a proper rational polynomial³ $P(x)/Q(x)$, if the denominator can be factored into the following form

$$Q(x) = (x+a)(x^3+b)(x^2+c)^2(x+d)^3,$$

then,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} &= \frac{A}{x+a} + \frac{Bx^2+Cx+D}{x^3+b} + \frac{Ex+F}{x^2+c} \\ &+ \frac{Gx+H}{(x^2+c)^2} + \frac{I}{x+d} + \frac{J}{(x+d)^2} + \frac{K}{(x+d)^3} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The following is another useful formula (from page 285 of the Tenenbaum and Pollard, 1963):

Given

$$\frac{1}{f(x)} = \frac{1}{(x-r_1)(x-r_2)\dots(x-r_k)\dots(x-r_n)},$$

where r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n are distinct. Then,

$$\frac{1}{f(x)} = \frac{1}{f'(r_1)(x-r_1)} + \frac{1}{f'(r_2)(x-r_2)} + \dots + \frac{1}{f'(r_n)(x-r_n)}, \quad (24)$$

in which $f'(r_k)$ is the derivative of $f(x)$ evaluated at $x = r_k$.

³That is, $P(x)$ is of degree less than $Q(x)$.

4.1 General form of inverse z-transforms

This is a summary of results on pages 263-264 of Luenberger's book.

Let $F(z)$ be a reduced strictly proper rational function

$$F(z) = \frac{b_{n-1}z^{n-1} + \dots + b_0}{z^n + a_{n-1}z^{n-1} + \dots + a_0}. \quad (25)$$

If the denominator of equation 25 can be factored in the form of

$$(z - z_1)(z - z_2)\dots(z - z_n),$$

with z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n distinct. Then, the rational function can be written in partial fraction form as

$$F(z) = \frac{c_1}{z - z_1} + \frac{c_2}{z - z_2} + \dots + \frac{c_n}{z - z_n}. \quad (26)$$

After constants c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are determined by comparing Eqs. 26 and 25, the original function corresponding to Eq. 26 can be obtained by considering each term as a delayed geometric series with ratio z_i . That is,

$$f(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & k = 0 \\ c_1 z_1^{k-1} + c_2 z_2^{k-1} + \dots + c_n z_n^{k-1} & k \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

If in Eq. 26 a root z_i is not distinct but repeated m times. Then, the expansion (Eq. 26) must include higher order terms and the resulting solution (Eq. 27) must contain terms of $z_i^k, (k-1)z_i^{k-1}, (k-1)^2 z_i^{k-2}, \dots, (k-1)^{m-1} z_i^{k-m}$. For example, if z_i is repeated twice. Then Eq. 27 will look like

$$f(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & k = 0 \\ \dots + c_{i-1} z_{i-1}^{k-1} + c_{i1} z_i^{k-1} + c_{i2} (k-1) z_i^{k-2} + c_{i+1} z_{i+1}^{k-1} + \dots & k \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

4.2 Transform solution of difference/differential equations

I would like to expand the discussion of Example 4 on page 260. The purpose of this example problem is to find a z-transform of the following pulse

⁴On page 264, these terms are shown as $z_i^k, k z_i^{k-1}, k^2 z_i^{k-2}, \dots, k^{m-1} z_i^{k-m+1}$. I think these should be corrected as $z_i^{k-1}, (k-1) z_i^{k-2}, (k-1)^2 z_i^{k-3}, \dots, (k-1)^{m-1} z_i^{k-m}$.

function:

$$f(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq k < N \\ 0 & k \geq N \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

We will use Property 1 (on page 258) to find out the answer for this problem. The pulse of duration N of Eq. 29 can be seen as $f(k) = f_1(k) - f_2(k)$, where $f_1(k)$ is the unit step function defined as $f_1(k) = 1$ for all $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, and $f_2(k)$ is an N step delayed version of the unit step function ($f_1(k)$) defined as

$$f_2(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq k < N \\ 1 & k \geq N. \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

By “ N step delayed function”, we mean that, unlike $f_1(k)$ having a value of 1 starting at $k = 0$, $f_2(k)$ picks up the non-zero value (of 1) only after the first N values of k are passed, that is, it is delayed for N units until $k = N$. If the z-transforms for $f_1(k)$ and $f_2(k)$ are $F_1(z)$ and $F_2(z)$, respectively, the z-transform for $f(k)$ can be found immediately as $F(z) = F_1(z) - F_2(z)$ (according to Property 1).

As the unit step function $f(k) = 1$ (for all $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) has the z-transform of $\frac{z}{z-1}$, and from Property 2 (page 259, applied N times) it is easy to see that the z-transform for $f_2(k)$ is $\frac{z}{z-1} \cdot \frac{1}{z^N}$. As a result, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F(z) &= \frac{z}{z-1} - \frac{z}{z-1} \cdot \frac{1}{z^N} \\ &= \frac{z^N - 1}{z^{N-1}(z-1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

If $N = 1$, Equation 31 will become $F(z) = 1$, which is compatible with the first entry of Table 8-1 (on page 261) for the z-transform of the unit impulse function

$$f(k) = \begin{cases} 1 & k = 0 \\ 0 & k \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

The difference equation describing geometric growth, $x(k+1) = ax(k)$, was solved recursively as shown on Page 5. Here we can also use the z transform to solve it. Using Property 3 (Page 259), we can transform both sides of the equation as $zX(z) - zx(0) = aX(z)$. After re-arranging, we have

$$X(z) = \frac{x(0)z}{z-a}. \quad (33)$$

Applying Property 1 (Page 258) and using Table on Page 261, we can find the solution by inverse transform: $x(k) = x(0)a^k$.

4.3 Solving differential equations using Laplace transform: a few examples

Problem 10 (page 311). Use Laplace transform to solve each of the following differential equations, with initial conditions $y(0) = 0, \dot{y}(0) = 1$.

$$\frac{d^2y}{dt^2} + \frac{dy}{dt} - 6y = 1 \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{d^2y}{dt^2} - y = e^{-t} \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{d^2y}{dt^2} + \frac{dy}{dt} + y = te^{-t} \quad (36)$$

4.3.1 Solution to Eq. 34

To apply the Laplace transform to the whole equation is equivalent to applying the transform to individual terms one by one. We know

$$\mathfrak{L}\left\{\frac{d^2y}{dt^2}\right\} = s^2Y(s) - sy(0) - \frac{dy}{dt}(0) = s^2Y(s) - 1$$

$$\mathfrak{L}\left\{\frac{dy}{dt}\right\} = sY(s) - y(0) = sY(s)$$

$$\mathfrak{L}\{1\} = \frac{1}{s}$$

\therefore Laplace transform for Eq. 34 is

$$s^2Y(s) - 1 + sY(s) - 6Y(s) = \frac{1}{s}$$

Collecting like terms and re-arranging yields,

$$Y(s) = \frac{1 + s}{s(s + 3)(s - 2)}.$$

Applying partial fraction expansion, we have,

$$Y(s) = \frac{A}{s} + \frac{B}{s + 3} + \frac{C}{s - 2},$$

where $A = -\frac{1}{6}$, $B = -\frac{2}{15}$, and $C = \frac{3}{10}$.

\therefore the above partial fraction expansion becomes,

$$Y(s) = -\frac{1}{6} \cdot \frac{1}{s} - \frac{2}{15} \cdot \frac{1}{s+3} + \frac{3}{10} \cdot \frac{1}{s-2}.$$

Remembering the following Laplace transform pairs

$$1 \longleftarrow \frac{1}{s}, \quad e^{-3t} \longleftarrow \frac{1}{s+3}, \quad e^{2t} \longleftarrow \frac{1}{s-2},$$

we can then find the solution to Eq. 34 by applying the inverse Laplace transform:

$$y(t) = -\frac{1}{6} - \frac{2}{15}e^{-3t} + \frac{3}{10}e^{2t}. \quad (37)$$

4.3.2 Solution to Eq. 35

The given initial conditions dictate that the 2nd order derivative of y has a Laplace transform of

$$\mathfrak{L} \left\{ \frac{d^2y}{dt^2} \right\} = s^2Y(s) - 1.$$

Also, we know that

$$\mathfrak{L} \{ e^{-t} \} = \frac{1}{s+1}.$$

So, applying forward Laplace transform to both sides of Eq. 35, we have

$$sY(s) - 1 - Y(s) = \frac{1}{s+1}.$$

Re-arranging and collecting like terms, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Y(s) &= \frac{2+s}{(s+1)(s^2-1)} \\ &= \frac{2+s}{(s+1)^2(s-1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Applying partial fraction expansion, we have,

$$\begin{aligned} Y(s) &= \frac{c_1}{s+1} + \frac{c_2}{(s+1)^2} + \frac{c_3}{s-1} \\ &= \frac{(c_1+c_3)s^2 + (c_2+2c_3)s - c_1 - c_2 + c_3}{(s+1)^2(s-1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

Comparing Eqs. 38 and 39, we obtain the following system of equations

$$\begin{cases} c_1 + c_3 & = 0 \\ c_2 + 2c_3 & = 1 \\ -c_1 - c_2 + c_3 & = 2 \end{cases}$$

Solving the above system of equations we have $c_1 = -3/4$, $c_2 = -1/2$, $c_3 = 3/4$. Thus Eq. 39 becomes

$$Y(s) = \frac{-3/4}{s+1} - \frac{1/2}{(s+1)^2} + \frac{3/4}{s-1}. \quad (40)$$

To invert Eq. 40 into time-domain form, we need first to find out the corresponding Laplace transforms for $1/(s+1)$, $1/(s+1)^2$, and $1/(s-1)$. We know the inverse transform for $1/(s+1)$ is e^{-t} , and that for $1/(s-1)$ is e^t . So, we now try to find out the inverse transform for $1/(s+1)^2$.

We know, if $F(s) = 1/(s+1)$, then,

$$\frac{dF(s)}{ds} = -\frac{1}{(s+1)^2}.$$

And there is formula for Laplace transform of a function multiplied by the independent variable:

$$tf(t) \longleftarrow -\frac{dF(s)}{ds}$$

Thus the inverse transform for $1/(s+1)^2$ should be te^{-t} . As a result, Eq. 40 can be inverted to obtain the time-domain equation as

$$y(t) = -\frac{3}{4}e^{-t} - \frac{1}{2}te^{-t} + \frac{3}{4}e^t,$$

which is the solution to Eq. 35.

4.3.3 Solution to Eq. 36

Based on our experiences in solving Eqs. 34 and 35, we can immediately write the Laplace transform to Eq. 36 as

$$s^2Y(s) - 1 + sY(s) + Y(s) = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2}. \quad (41)$$

Collecting like terms and re-arranging, we have

$$Y(s) = \frac{s^2 + 2s + 2}{(1+s)^2(s^2 + s + 1)}. \quad (42)$$

The appropriate partial fraction expansion for Eq. 42 takes the form of

$$Y(s) = \frac{A}{1+s} + \frac{B}{(1+s)^2} + \frac{Cs + D}{(s^2 + s + 1)}. \quad (43)$$

Solving, we have⁵ $A = B = 1, C = -1, D = 0$. Thus, Eq. 43 becomes

$$Y(s) = \frac{1}{1+s} + \frac{1}{(1+s)^2} - \frac{s}{(s^2 + s + 1)}. \quad (44)$$

In solving Eqs. 34 and 35, we already know the Laplace transforms for $1/(1+s)$ and $1/(1+s)^2$. Now we only need to figure out the appropriate inverse transform for the 3rd term of Eq. 44. We know the inverse transform of $(s-a)/((s-a)^2 + \omega^2)$ is $e^{at} \cos \omega t$. So, it is possible to re-arrange $s/(s^2 + s + 1)$ into a form that has an inverse of transform of something like $e^{at} \cos \omega t$ or $e^{at} \sin \omega t$, or a combination of them. Indeed, actually we can do it.

Recognizing that $s^2 + s + 1 = (s + 1/2)^2 + 3/4$, we have

$$-\frac{s}{s^2 + s + 1} = -\frac{s + \frac{1}{2}}{(s + \frac{1}{2})^2 + (\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}})^2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}}{(s + \frac{1}{2})^2 + (\sqrt{\frac{3}{4}})^2}. \quad (45)$$

And this immediately allows us to write

$$\mathfrak{L}^{-1} \left\{ -\frac{s}{s^2 + s + 1} \right\} = -e^{-\frac{t}{2}} \cos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}t + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} e^{-\frac{t}{2}} \sin \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}t.$$

As a result, the inverse Laplace transform for Eq. 44 is

$$y(t) = (1+t)e^{-t} + \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \sin \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}t - \cos \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}t \right) e^{-\frac{t}{2}},$$

which is the solution to Eq. 36. This solution, as well as solutions to Eqs. 34 and 35, was verified through substitution into the original equation.

⁵Here we must note that the numerator for the 2nd term of Eq. 43 contains a constant only (here it is B without an s term). However, the numerator of the 3rd term of this same equation must contain an s term! Also see Eq. 23.

4.4 Solving difference equations using z transform: comments and a few examples

An interesting implication of Theorem 3 (on page 29 of the Luenberger book) is that an arbitrary solution $z(k)$ to the n th order homogeneous equation (11-3) (see page 28) is linked to the n initial conditions leading to this solution by the following relation:

$$z(k) = c_1 \bar{z}_1(k) + c_2 \bar{z}_2(k) + \dots + c_n \bar{z}_n(k) \quad (46)$$

where $c_i = z(i - 1)$ represents the i th initial condition and $\bar{z}_1(k)$, $\bar{z}_2(k)$, ..., $\bar{z}_n(k)$ are n fundamental solutions. I read Theorem 3 several times but still cannot understand why it has been proved, except that I can see the important implication as stated here.

Let us elaborate the steps for finding out the two fundamental solutions for the second order difference equation (Example 2 on page 30 of the Luenberger book). First, let's restate the equation

$$z(k + 2) - 2z(k + 1) + z(k) = 0. \quad (47)$$

Here “ $z(k + 2)$ ” should be read as “function of z evaluated at point $(k + 2)$ ”, instead of “ z multiplied by $(k + 2)$ ”⁶. For this second order equation, there are only two fundamental solutions: one is that obtained from initial conditions of $z(0) = 1$ and $z(1) = 0$; and the other is from initial conditions of $z(0) = 0$ and $z(1) = 1$. The two fundamental solutions are those that can be obtained based on the two sets of initial conditions. We will use the z -transform to find the two solutions. For notational convenience, let us use $x()$ ⁷ instead of $z()$ to represent Eq. 47. Using the z transform (looking at Eq. 47 from the frequency domain), Eq. 47 becomes⁸,

$$\overbrace{z^2 X(z) - z^2 x(0) - zx(1)}^{x(k+2)} - 2 \overbrace{[zX(z) - zx(0)]}^{x(k+1)} + X(z) = 0. \quad (48)$$

Collecting like terms we get

$$X(z) = \frac{z^2 - 2z}{z^2 - 2z + 1}. \quad (49)$$

⁶For those people like myself who do not use difference equations on a daily basis, this remind is sometimes useful.

⁷Then, it becomes $x(k + 2) - 2x(k + 1) + x(k) = 0$. This notational change will reserve z for the frequency domain variable corresponding to the time domain variable k .

⁸In this case we use the z transform formula for advanced sequence as shown in page 259 of the Luenberger book.

Next we will convert the right-hand side of Eq. 49 into partial fraction form, which will be helpful for us to obtain the solution to Eq. 47 through inverse z transform. However, as the above polynomial is not *strictly proper*⁹, we will use a hint from page 265 of the Luenberger book to do it. Specifically, we will first do a partial fraction expansion for

$$\frac{X(z)}{z} = \frac{z - 2}{z^2 - 2z + 1}. \quad (50)$$

Based on formula provided on the book of Tenenbaum and Pollard (1963)¹⁰, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{X(z)}{z} &= \frac{z - 2}{(z - 1)^2} \\ &= \frac{A}{z - 1} + \frac{B}{(z - 1)^2} \\ &= \frac{Az - (A - B)}{(z - 1)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

From the above, we can deduce that $A = 1$, $B = -1$. And thus the partial fraction expansion of Eq. 50 becomes

$$\frac{X(z)}{z} = \frac{1}{z - 1} - \frac{1}{(z - 1)^2}. \quad (51)$$

Multiplying both sides of Eq. 51 by z we then obtain the partial fraction expansion of $X(z)$:

$$X(z) = \frac{z}{z - 1} - \frac{z}{(z - 1)^2}. \quad (52)$$

Using inverse z transform¹¹, we can obtain the first fundamental solution corresponding to the initial conditions of $z(0) = 1$ and $z(1) = 0$:

$$x(k) = 1 - k.$$

Using the same approach we can find the second fundamental solution (corresponding to initial conditions of $z(0) = 0$ and $z(1) = 1$) as

$$x(k) = k(k > 0).$$

⁹See page 263 of the Luenberger book.

¹⁰M. Tenenbaum and H. Pollard. 1963, Ordinary Differential Equations. Harper & Row Publishers. Pages 284-285.

¹¹See Table 8-1 of page 261 of the Luenberger book.

Here the restriction of $k > 0$ is important, because we need to use formula of delay geometric series and delayed geometric ramp¹² to convert following z transform (from the second set of initial conditions) back to the time domain equation¹³:

$$X(z) = \frac{1}{(z-1)} + \frac{1}{(z-1)^2}. \quad (53)$$

4.4.1 Solution to Exercise 17 (b) and (e) using z transform

Solve the following difference equations (page 52 of the Luenberger book):

$$y(k+2) - 5y(k+1) + 6y(k) = 0, y(0) = y(1) = 1 \quad (54)$$

and

$$y(k+2) - 3y(k+1) + 2y(k) = 1, y(0) = y(1) = 2. \quad (55)$$

Solutions: The above two equations are both second order difference equations¹⁴. We will use the z transform to solve them. Remember that, if the z transform of sequence $y(k)$ is $Y(z)$, then the transform of the advanced sequence $y(k+1)$ is $zY(z) - zy(0)$ ¹⁵, and the transform of the twice advanced sequence $y(k+2)$ can be obtained by applying Property 2 twice, yielding $z^2Y(z) - z^2y(0) - zy(1)$.

Subjecting both sides of Eq. 54 to the z transform and collecting like terms, we get

$$Y(z) = \frac{z^2 - 4z}{z^2 - 5z + 6}.$$

Next we will use partial fraction expansion to decompose the right hand side of the above equation so that to find the solution to Eq. 54 through inverse z transform. As the right hand side of the above equation is not a strictly proper polynomial, we will divide both sides of the equation by z so that the

¹²Again, see page 261 of the Luenberger book.

¹³That is, to find the solution to the original difference equation corresponding to this second set of initial conditions.

¹⁴For an n th order equation, n initial conditions must be provided in order to obtain the solution.

¹⁵Property 2 as discussed on page 259 of the Luenberger book.

right hand side can be expressed as partial fractions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{Y(z)}{z} &= \frac{z-4}{(z-2)(z-3)} \\
&= \frac{A}{(z-2)} + \frac{B}{(z-3)} \\
&= \frac{(A+B)z - (3A-2B)}{(z-2)(z-3)} \\
&= \frac{2}{z-2} - \frac{1}{z-3}.
\end{aligned}$$

So the z transform of Eq. 54 becomes

$$Y(z) = 2\frac{z}{z-2} - \frac{z}{z-3},$$

from which the solution to Eq. 54 is obtained through the inverse z transform:

$$y(k) = 2^{k+1} - 3^k. \quad (56)$$

Substituting this solution into Eq. 54 and we verified that it is a solution.

To solve Eq. 55, we apply the z transform to both sides of the equation and collect like terms to yield

$$Y(z) = \frac{z}{(z-1)^2(z-2)} + \frac{2z}{(z-1)}.$$

Applying the partial fraction expansion to the first polynomial of the right hand side of the above equation, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y(z) &= \frac{z}{(z-1)^2(z-2)} + \frac{2z}{(z-1)} \\
&= \frac{A}{(z-1)} + \frac{B}{(z-1)^2} + \frac{C}{(z-2)} + \frac{2z}{(z-1)} \\
&= \frac{(A+C)z^2 - (3A-B+2C)z + (2A-2B+C)}{(z-1)^2(z-2)} + \frac{2z}{(z-1)} \\
&= -\frac{2}{(z-1)} - \frac{1}{(z-1)^2} + \frac{2}{z-2} + \frac{2z}{(z-1)}.
\end{aligned}$$

Using the inverse z -transform, the solution to Eq. 55 can be obtained as

$$y(k) = 2^k - k + 1. \quad (57)$$

Substituting this solution into Eq. 55 and we verified that it is indeed a solution.

4.4.2 Solutions to Exercise 17 (b) and (e) using the characteristic equation

When we used the z transform to solve Eqs. 54 and 55, actually we did not use the provided initial conditions. These conditions are useful if we solve the above two equations using the method of characteristic equations.

The characteristics equation for the homogeneous equation 54 is

$$\lambda^2 - 5\lambda + 6 = 0,$$

which has two real roots $\lambda = 2$ and $\lambda = 3$. Thus the general solution to Eq. 54 is

$$y(k) = C_1 2^k + C_2 3^k.$$

Plugging the two initial conditions ($y(0) = y(1) = 1$) into the above general solution yield $C_1 = 2$ and $C_2 = -1$. This means that the solution of Eq. 54 is

$$y(k) = 2^{k+1} - 3^k,$$

which is identical to Eq. 56.

Equation 55 is a non-homogeneous equation. To solve it using method of characteristics equation, we first need to find out one arbitrary solution. As the right hand side of the equation is not a geometric series but the integer 1, we first try to see if $y(k) = 1 - k$ is a solution¹⁶. Plugging the trial solution into the equation and it satisfies the equation. Next will obtain a general solution to the corresponding homogeneous equation. As the roots for the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^2 - 3\lambda + 2 = 0$$

are $\lambda = 2$ and $\lambda = 1$, the general solution to Eq. 55 is the sum of the arbitrary solution ($y(k) = 1 - k$) and the the general solution to the homogeneous equation:

$$y(k) = C_1 2^k + C_2 + 1 - k.$$

Applying the initial conditions $y(0) = y(1) = 2$, the arbitrary coefficients C_1 and C_2 can be determined as $C_1 = 1$ and $C_2 = 0$. Thus the solution to the non-homogeneous difference equation 55 becomes

$$y(k) = 2^k - k + 1,$$

which is identical to Eq. 57.

¹⁶If the right hand side is a geometric series, then we try using a similar geometric series as a solution.

4.4.3 Solution to exercise 17(a) on page 52

Solve the following difference equation

$$(k+2)^2 y(k+1) - (k+1)^2 y(k) = 2k+3, y(0) = 0. \quad (58)$$

As $(k+2)^2$ is not zero ($k \geq 0$), the above equation can be changed into

$$y(k+1) - \frac{(k+1)^2}{(k+2)^2} y(k) = \frac{2k+3}{(k+2)^2}.$$

As this is not a constant coefficient equation, we cannot use the characteristic equation method to solve it. As we are given the initial value, we might try forward recursion method. We observe that the $y(k+1)$ is obtained by multiplying $y(k)$ by $\frac{(k+1)^2}{(k+2)^2}$. This suggests a geometric series. For notational ease, let $a = \frac{(k+1)^2}{(k+2)^2}$ and $b = \frac{2k+3}{(k+2)^2}$. So, the difference equation now has the form of¹⁷

$$y(k+1) - ay(k) = a.$$

Using forward recursion, we have

$$\begin{aligned} y(0) &= 0 \\ y(1) &= b \\ y(2) &= b(1+a) \\ y(3) &= b(1+a+a^2) \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \\ y(k) &= b(1+a+a^2+\dots+a^{k-1}). \end{aligned}$$

As a result the solution to Eq. 58, after collecting like terms and simplifying, is

$$y(k) = 1 - \left[\frac{(k+1)^2}{(k+2)^2} \right]^k.$$

I still don't understand why in computer the above expression can be executed correctly but the expression

$$y(k) = 1 - \frac{(k+1)^{2k}}{(k+2)^{2k}}$$

can not¹⁸.

¹⁷However, here both a and b are functions of k and cannot be considered as constants.

¹⁸For $k \in [0, 80]$, it is OK, but for $k \geq 81$ it does not work.

4.4.4 Solution to Exercise 1 on page 47

Solve the nonlinear difference equation

$$y(k+1) = \frac{y(k)}{b+y(k)} \quad (59)$$

by finding a change of variable that converts it to a linear difference equation.

Solution. This nonlinear difference equation is important in genetics (see page 389). To change it into a linear form, we let $x(k) = 1/y(k)$. Then the original problem becomes:

$$x(k+1) = bx(k) + 1.$$

Applying z-transform to both sides of the above equation (see page 261 of the Luenberger Book), we have

$$zX(z) - zx(0) = bX(z) + \frac{z}{z-1}.$$

Re-arranging and using partial fraction expansion, we have

$$\begin{aligned} X(z) &= \frac{z}{(z-1)(z-b)} + x(0)\frac{z}{z-b} \\ &= \frac{1}{1-b} \cdot \frac{1}{z-1} - \frac{b}{1-b} \cdot \frac{1}{z-b} + x(0)\frac{z}{z-b}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we apply the inverse z-transform to the above equation (note that the frequency-domain terms $1/(z-1)$ and $1/(z-b)$ represent delayed geometric series of 1 and b^{k-1} , respectively, in the time domain; the frequency-domain term $z/(z-b)$ represents a geometric series of a^k in the time domain¹⁹):

$$\begin{aligned} x(k) &= \frac{1}{1-b} - \frac{b}{1-b}b^{k-1} + x(0)b^k \\ &= \frac{1-b^k}{1-b} + x(0)b^k. \end{aligned}$$

Re-arranging and taking into consideration the fact that $x(k) = 1/y(k)$, we then obtain the solution of Eq. 59 as

$$y(k) = \begin{cases} 1-b & k=0 \\ \frac{y(0)(1-b)}{y(0)(1-b^k)+b^k(1-b)} & k \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (60)$$

¹⁹These hold under assumption of $k > 0$; for $k = 0$, these time domain terms are all zero.

Apparently, the above solution exists under the assumption of $b \neq 1$. If $b = 1$, Eq. 59 will become

$$y(k+1) = \frac{y(k)}{1+y(k)}, \quad (61)$$

which has a solution of $y(k) = A/(1 + Ak)$, with $A = y(0)$ (see page 17 of the Luenberger Book). The above solution can be found using the similar approach as the one for solving Eq. 59. After transforming the nonlinear equation into the linear form, we have

$$x(k+1) = x(k) + 1.$$

Applying z-transform, we have

$$zX(z) - zx(0) = \frac{z}{z-1} + X(z).$$

Collecting the like terms, we obtain the expression of $X(z)$ as:

$$X(z) = \frac{z}{(z-1)^2} + x(0)\frac{z}{z-1}.$$

Realizing that $z/(z-1)^2$ corresponds to the unit ramp ($x(k) = k$) in time domain, and $1/(z-1)$ represents the unit step ($x(k) = 1$), we thus obtain the corresponding equation in the time domain as:

$$x(k) = k + x(0).$$

By converting the equation back in terms of the original variable $y(k)$, we have

$$\frac{1}{y(k)} = k + \frac{1}{y(0)},$$

which, after re-arranging, becomes

$$y(k) = \frac{y(0)}{1 + y(0)k}. \quad (62)$$

This is the solution to Eq. 61.

4.5 Additional topics

Show that the following n th order derivative for the exponential function $e^{\lambda t}$ holds:

$$\frac{d^n(e^{\lambda t})}{dt^n} = \lambda^n e^{\lambda t}, \quad (63)$$

assuming λ is a constant. We only verify the above relation using 2nd and 3rd order derivatives. For the 2nd order derivative, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^2}{dt^2} [e^{\lambda t}] &= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{d}{dt} (e^{\lambda t}) \right] \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{d}{d(\lambda t)} (e^{\lambda t}) \frac{d}{dt} (\lambda t) \right] \\
&= \lambda \frac{d}{dt} [e^{\lambda t}] \\
&= \lambda \frac{d}{d(\lambda t)} [e^{\lambda t}] \frac{d}{dt} [\lambda t] \\
&= \lambda^2 e^{\lambda t}.
\end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

Now we verify Eq. 63 using the 3rd order derivative:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d^3}{dt^3} [e^{\lambda t}] &= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{d}{dt} e^{\lambda t} \right] \right] \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{d}{dt} [e^{\lambda t} \lambda] \right] \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} \left[\lambda \frac{d}{dt} e^{\lambda t} \right] \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} [\lambda^2 e^{\lambda t}] \\
&= \lambda^2 \frac{d}{dt} [e^{\lambda t}] \\
&= \lambda^2 e^{\lambda t} \lambda \\
&= \lambda^3 e^{\lambda t}.
\end{aligned} \tag{65}$$